

TEACHING METHODOLOGY USING SPEECH GAMES IN RUSSIAN LANGUAGE CLASSES AT A MILITARY UNIVERSITY**Ruziyeva Umida Todjiboyevna**

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Abstract. *This article is about the relevance of the study is determined by the pragmatic approach to teaching the Russian language to military personnel from the CIS countries who speak Russian (cadets, students, adjuncts). The training involves preparing them for military activities in Russian.*

Key words: *linguodidactic, intensive training, internal and external speech, hypothesis.*

ТЕКСТ НАУЧНОЙ РАБОТЫ НА ТЕМУ «МЕТОДИКА ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ С ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕМ РЕЧЕВЫХ ИГР НА ЗАНЯТИЯХ ПО РУССКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ В ВОЕННОМ ВУЗЕ»

Аннотация. *В данной статье речь идет об актуальности исследования, определяемой прагматическим подходом к обучению русскому языку военнослужащих из стран СНГ, владеющих русским языком (курсантов, курсантов, адъюнктов). Обучение предполагает подготовку их к боевым действиям на русском языке.*

Ключевые слова: *лингводидактика, интенсивное обучение, внутренняя и внешняя речь, гипотеза.*

INTRODUCTION

In the last decade, standard Russian language programs for students at a Russian military university have included a new educational and program block - training in military business speech. Until now, this linguodidactic problem has not been sufficiently developed, the first results of its solution are presented by Shatalova N.S. (1999), A.A. (2002). However, the problem of teaching military business correspondence as one of the leading speech and professional skills of a serviceman was not raised in these works. Therefore, the search for effective methods for the formation of these skills and abilities remains relevant. To solve this linguodidactic task, it is necessary to develop a methodology for business games, and in such a variant as speech games.

When conducting speech games, the skills and abilities of mastering military business correspondence are corrected and improved. The choice of the method of speech games is determined by the existing contradictions:

-between the existing need for intensive training of military business speech for military personnel of the CIS countries in the practical course of the Russian language and the course "Russian Language and Culture of Speech" and the lack of development of the content of training and methods for developing the skills and abilities of mastering military business correspondence;

-between the volume of language material necessary for studying and the limited study time allotted for the study of these program topics;

-between the existing possibility of using new technologies in the educational process in the Russian language and the lack of a linguistic description of the genres of military correspondence and their correspondence to linguodidactic interpretation. Thus, the relevance of this study is determined by the need: linguistic and linguo-didactic description of the genres of military business correspondence to ensure the process of teaching military business speech to a contingent of students in a military university; inclusion in the theory and practice of teaching the Russian language in a military university of purposeful work on the texts of military business correspondence. developing the content of thematic speech games and creating their methodology. Following A.F. Zhuravlev, N.S. Shatalova, and A.A. Schischisok, who studied military business speech and the methodology for studying it, military business speech is defined as a variety of Russian business speech that dominates in the military sphere and environment. These researchers emphasize that military business speech is realized in oral and written forms of speech communication in the military sphere and environment, in internal and external speech contacts of the army with society and the state, in international contacts of the army with society and states, in international contacts of the Armed Forces of the Russian Federation with armies of sovereign states. [1,68-74p].

RESEARCH METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

Military business speech is a phenomenon of Russian military speech communication. The study draws attention to the fact that free military business communication can be achieved when students have an idea about the features of the speech organization of military business correspondence texts and military business speech skills and abilities will be formed on this material. The formation of skills and abilities to master military business correspondence requires a teacher to have a high methodological and ideological level of teaching. It is important to focus on a specific object of verbal communication - texts of military business correspondence, education of speech behavior and speech ethics on the basis of military business communication in the general program block "Military Business Speech".

The complex work is based on information about the extralinguistic and intralinguistic parameters of military business correspondence genres. The study was conducted as part of the formation of speech skills necessary and sufficient for writing military business letters, texts of orders, instructions, reports, instructions, reports, acts, reports, protocols, and references.

It was necessary to find pedagogical means of formation and improvement of military-business written communication, skills and abilities to use the state language of the Russian Federation that are relevant for training. The most important condition for the formation of the skills and abilities of military business correspondence is to determine the nature and content of the motivational component of training, which makes it possible to quickly involve trainees in educational and cognitive activities. Such a motivational component can be created under the condition of using business games in the educational process in one of their variants - in speech games [3, 150-153 p].

RESEARCH RESULT AND DISCUSSION

All of the above served as the basis for choosing the topic of this study - "Methods for teaching military business correspondence using speech games in Russian language classes at a military university." The object of the research is teaching the Russian language in the program section "Military Business Speech: Military Business Correspondence" using speech games.

The subject of the research is the intensification of the process of teaching military business speech in one of its subsystems: "Military business correspondence" using speech games.

The purpose of this study is to develop the content of the methodology of speech games "Military Business Correspondence"; creating a system of thematic speech games that form, correct and improve the skills of military business correspondence, which are based on situational speech exercises. The inclusion of speech games in the educational process is carried out in order to achieve the optimal level of possession of these skills and abilities. Based on the linguistic description of the texts of military business correspondence and their linguodidactic commentary, a research hypothesis was put forward; successful training in military business speech at a military university is possible if training in military business correspondence is carried out on the basis of using an effective method of speech games that focus students' attention on the features of business speech communication in the military sphere and environment. The dominant form of work in the course of speech games will be complex work with the genres of military business correspondence: military business letter, order, instruction, report, order, report, act, report, protocol, reference.

The technique of speech games will be used at the stage of final communication, and the skills and abilities of military business correspondence are considered as an obligatory component of the speech training of a future military specialist, which involves the use of a comprehensive description of the speech organization of texts: a military business letter, an order, an instruction, a report, an order, a report, act, report, protocol, reference for educational purposes [4, 67-78 p].

In accordance with the purpose and hypothesis, the research tasks were solved;

1) Clarify, expand and systematize linguistic information about the genres of military business correspondence: military business letter, order, instruction, report, order, memorandum, act, report, protocol, reference, give their linguistic description.

2) To identify the skills and abilities of mastering military business correspondence in the structure of the speech training of students in a military university that meets the current program requirements and traditionally used methods for the formation of these skills.

3) In accordance with the requirements of the experimental military business correspondence training program, formulate frequency-normative, systemic, logical-functional principles for the formation, correction and improvement of military business correspondence skills, including compositional and graphic skills and abilities.

4) Outline the stages of formation of skills and abilities of military business correspondence, determine their sequence.

5) Determine the stages of correction and improvement of these skills and abilities in the course of speech games.

6) Experimentally check and test the content of the course of speech games "Military Business Correspondence".

The main research methods were:

1) didactic and meaningful analysis of gaming technologies - business games; 2) analysis of statistical data for the selection of educational texts of military business correspondence according to the frequency of their use; 3) experimental training; 4) monitoring the implementation of the experiment in the educational process; 5) questioning trainees in order

to identify their opinions about the experimental program; 6) analysis of quantitative and qualitative indicators of experimental work.

CONCLUSION

The texts of open military business correspondence served as the material for the study.

The study was carried out in three stages:

At the first stage (1997-1998), linguistic, psycholinguistic, pedagogical and linguodidactic literature was studied: the principles of linguistic and linguodidactic description of the genres of military business correspondence were clarified; an analysis was made of the use of gaming technologies in Russian civilian universities recommended for students from the CIS countries; theoretical and practical methods of constructing speech games were described; a frequency dictionary of military business correspondence was compiled, the data of which were used as a lexical and lexical-grammatical basis for the content of speech games.

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